

**Dr. Champak Bhakat (Scientist)
Incharge Camel Management Unit
National Research Centre on Camel
BIKANER-3340001 (Raj.)**

Indian J. Anim. Res., 35 (1): 10 - 14, 2001

IMPACT OF CAMEL PRODUCTION SYSTEM ON THE SUSTAINABILITY OF MARGINAL FARMERS IN HOT ARID VILLAGES OF THAR DESERT

Champak Bhakat and M.S. Sahani

NRCC, Bikaner - 334001, India

ABSTRACT

A grass root level survey was conducted on various aspects of camelid farming which involved four different zones (north, south, east, west) of Thar desert. The required data were collected in the suitable developed and pre - tested proforma from Raikas of Thar desert. In this region the camel to other herbivore (cattle, buffalo, sheep and goat) ratio was 1:21.36. Among the different camel health disorders, Parasitic mange case was highest. It was followed by Trypanosomiasis, general fever, respiratory infection, other problems like digestive disorders, worm etc. The mortality in camel calf (<1 year age) and adult were $33.05 \pm 2.63\%$ and $8.10 \pm 1.07\%$, respectively. The average annual productivity of commonly grown Thar desert crop were 4.89q/ha for guar (*Cyamopsis tetragonoloba*) and 2.75q/ha for moth(*Phaseolus aconitifolius*). The final returns per unit (Rupee) invested was high in case of guar (Rs. 3.36) as compared to Moth (Rs. 2.29). The average cost of rearing of draft camel was low as compared to cattle and buffalo. The final return per unit (Rupee) invested was high in case of camel (Rs. 1.90) as compared to cattle and buffalo (Rs. 1.82) in Thar desert. It is evident that due to higher production potential, increase market price and economic advantage guar cultivation for camel farmers is more profitable than moth cultivation and camel rearing is also profitable as compared to other livestock rearing in terms of per unit investment.

INTRODUCTION

India is a highly populated country with 32 states/ UT's with 81 regions having their varying regional perspective. The total population that nears 1000 million with 50% females among them, with 46% people are between the age group of 19 yrs and 60 yrs i.e they are eligible to be in employment but the opportunity of organised employment (salaried jobs) are limited to less than 3% and about 70% of country's population is dependent on agriculture/animal husbandry (Singh,2000). As crop fields are low in desert land, because of recurrent drought the farmers of the region rely heavily on livestock enterprises for their sustenance. Animal husbandary under such degraded lands can be successful only if the livestock are basically a stable protective resource having long term viability employment-absorbing capability and income generating capacity. The livestock should be compatible with crop cultivation instead of competing with it for land and water resource. Camel rearing enterprise fits well with such requirements. The

total world camel population is estimated to be 19.286 million of which India has third highest camel population of 1.52 million (FAO, 1998) after Somalia and Sudan. Indian camel population is mainly confined to northwestern states viz: Rajasthan, Gujrat, Haryana and Punjab (93.12% of total Indian camel population) with highest intensity of camel in eleven arid district of Rajasthan (70.13% of total Indian camel population) (Khanna *et al.*, 1990). In India nearly 41.4 per cent of the country's total landmass of 3.28 million sq. km falls in the category of arid (11.8%) and semi-arid (29.6%) zones. Camel is associated with social culture of the societies inhabiting in the dry lands. Marketing of camel is an important trade in the Rajasthan where it is widely used as draft animal. Camel carts continue to play a crucial role in the farm economy as a cheap mode of short distance transportation of different agricultural commodities. Since 85% of the gross cultivated area of the Bikaner district is non-irrigated camel carts hold a significant potential for financing (Amresh Kumar 1999).

Camel power for farming use is more economical than a pair of bullocks and in the sandy terrain the camel energy is not only cost effective but also profitable and remunerable. Kohler- Rollefson (1992) focused on Raikas breeders of Rajasthan. Rapid change in agroecological condition and industrialisation in the recent past has its impact on camel management practices. In order to obtain optimum profit from camel, it is essential to adopt scientific management practices.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Data collection : The required data were collected in the suitably developed and pre- tested proforma by survey method during the year 1999 - 2000. This grass root level survey covered various aspects of camel rearing system viz. social status of camel keepers, ongoing agriculture practices, number of livestock, their camel breeding practices, Commonly occurring diseases, health status, production aspects and sources of revenue of camel keepers etc.

Sampling Procedure: The selection of respondents was made by using stratified random sampling technique. The study involved a total of five different villages which are representing five tehsils of Bikaner and Churu district. Five different tehsils were categories into four different zone of Thar desert, viz: Nokha tehsil (South zone), Lunkarensar tehsil (North zone), Kolayat tehsil (West zone) and Sri Dungargarh tehsil (East zone). A sample of 11 to 14 households were drawn from each village randomly for data collection.

Economic analysis: To obtain the estimates of rearing cost of animal and cost of crop cultivation, the opportunity cost of owned inputs and actual prices paid by the farmers for purchasing inputs were considered. To work out the gross returns from different source of income of farmers, the market prices were considered. Finally, the economic estimates were carried out by tabular analysis.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The socio-economic status of camel keepers as well as communication and transport infrastructure are also very poor. In these districts land is dune and soils are low in nitrogen and organic matter content. It is naturally eroded by winds during Summer and the crop yields are low and unstable. Some of camel keepers follow a trans migratory system of animal management. Animal husbandry in this region depends not only on the economic and social aspects of the migrating farmers but also on the ecological and agrostological aspects of land use management.

In this study the average family size of camel farmers ranges from 5.25 ± 1.33 to 8.54 ± 2.66 with overall average of 6.70 ± 0.59 individuals. The overall number of female members are 3.49 ± 0.26 where as male members are 3.21 ± 0.36 . The literacy percentage varies from 26.22 to 32.11. Most of camel keepers are having maximum non-irrigated land. The overall average land holding was 29.90 ± 1.01 ha/farmer (Non irrigated) and 15.22 ± 1.02 ha/farmer (irrigated). Among the different categories of farmer marginal farmer formed the major group (92.50 to 96.14%) and few progressive farmers (3.86 to 7.50%) are also there. National sample survey 1991-92 indicates that there are 62.8% marginal farmers and 17.8% small holders. There had been a steady decrease in the size of land holding per person (Singh 2000). It was observed that under village condition the female members of farmers family devoted maximum time (81.85%) as compared to male members (18.15%) with day to day management of camel. The major crop of kharif season are guar, moth, bajra, mung, til etc. where as under irrigated belt, the rabi season's crops are mustard, chana, wheat etc.

The ratio of camel to other livestock species in different villages of Thar districts are presented in Table - 1. The camel to sheep &

age annual mortality in young camel calves (up to 1 month age) was maximum as compared to adult camel. The overall average annual mortality in young calves was $33.05\% \pm 2.63$ where as in adult, it was 8.10 ± 1.07 . As

ethnoveterinary practice camel farmers used mobile oil/ kerosine oil/ sesame oil and boric powder against mange infection, Alcohol + Onion for general fever and Azoan + Molasses for coughing problems.

Table 2. Frequency Distribution of different health disorders and mortality in camel of different zones of Thar districts.

Zones(Tehsils)	South (Nokha)	North (Lunkaransar)	West (Kolayat)	East (Dungargarh)	Overall	Ranking
Types of Disorders(%)						
Parasitic Mange	80.14	73.44	72.11	76.77	75.62 ± 1.80	I
Surra	11.20	15.00	12.24	12.71	12.79 ± 0.80	II
General Fever	3.52	5.21	6.15	4.57	4.86 ± 0.55	III
Respiratory Infection Pneumonia,(Coughing etc.)	2.99	3.35	5.70	3.83	3.96 ± 0.60	IV
Other Problems (Digestive disorder, Worm etc.)	2.15	3.00	3.80	2.12	2.76 ± 0.40	V
Death Rate(%)						
Adult	5.23 ± 1.44	9.15 ± 1.50	10.16 ± 2.61	7.86 ± 3.05	8.10 ± 1.07	II
Calf (<1yr aged)	28.26 ± 2.55	35.56 ± 3.51	39.24 ± 2.11	29.13 ± 2.15	33.05 ± 2.63	I

Economic Analysis of Camel keepers: The productivity of two major crop commonly grown in this study area and their cost of cultivation along with return in presented in Table- 3A. The per hectare productivity of guar was higher than moth. The average cost of cultivation were Rs. 3200/ha and Rs. 2525/ha for guar and desi moth respectively where as gross return from guar was higher than moth.

Return per rupee invested was higher in guar (Rs. 3.36) as compared to desi moth (Rs. 2.29). The same trend was observed in case of net return. From this study it is evident that due to higher production potential, increase market price and economic advantage guar cultivation for camel keeper is more profitable than traditional moth cultivation.

Table 3A. The Average economic return of camel keepers from agriculture

Major Crop	Aveg. Productivity(Q/Ha)	Aveg. cost of Cultivation. (Rs./Ha)	Gross Return (Rs./Ha)	Net Return (Rs./Ha)	Return /Rupee Invested (Rs.)
Guar	4.89	3200.00	10758.00	7558.00	3.36
Desi Moth	2.75	2525.00	5775.00	3250.00	2.29

The economic return of camel keepers from animal husbandry is presented in Table - 3B. The major return from different animal sources are taken for economic calculation. The average return from cattle and buffalo was 10 kg milk/day animal and from sheep was 2.50 kg wool/year/animal where as camel delivered return through carting. The average cost of rearing of camel was comparatively low as compared to cattle and buffalo. The

sheep were reared in zero input basis (mainly on kitchen waste/grazing land). The net return from cattle and buffalo was high (Rs. 45/day/animal) as compared to camel (Rs. 36/day/camel). The similar trend was observed in case of gross return. Return per rupee invested was high in case of camel as compared to cattle and buffalo. This is mainly due to low rearing cost of camel than cattle & buffalo. Khanna and Rai (1994) suggested to encourage camel

encouraged in the l. In that event there no loss to the land, as camel will cause ecology than other (1990).

Thar districts.

12.45
8.56
0.31
21.36

their cart camel. The ces required for con- ± 0.28 to 2.56 ± 0.27 . $72\% \pm 4.86$ reported on/rutting months is h where as few farm- d is from November

Discussion: Frequency of health disorders and different zones of Thar in Table - 2. The first parasitic mange with $52\% \pm 1.80$. It indicates parasitic mange problem/highest. This is as per *et al.* (1997). In south problems is maximum nce of surra (Trypano- 1.20% to 15.00% and only in irrigated area. It health disorders. General g with overall frequency ce of Respiratory infec- g etc) got IV rank- was highest (5.70%) at health problems like di- hoes form infestation e from 2.12% to 3.80%. res were adopted in vil- or bacterial diseases. Al- inst mange with Butox injection was reported and east zone. The aver-

as draft animal in arid regions. Saley (1993) reported that the main objectives of camel rearing in Rajasthan is obviously animal power for pulling a cart or ploughing. Rama *et al.* (1997) reported that the livestock farming has more or less been steady in spite of several severe droughts that the region experienced in recent years. There is a need for capital generation and raw material production for the industry to survive. An increase in demand for animal products in the urban consumer market is expected. C.M Singh (2000) suggested that the only source that is sustainable would be the small holder who generates products at moderate cost, without draining natural resources and depending on import.

Table 3B. The Average economic return of camel keepers from animal husbandry

Animal	Average Return	Aveg. Cost of rearing (Rs./ani/day)	Gross Return (Rs./ani/day)	Net Return (Rs./ani/day)	Return / Rupee Invested(Rs)
Cattle&Buffalo	Milk-10 kg/day/ani.	55	100	45	1.82
Sheep	Wool - 2.50 kg/Yr/Ani	0	213/Ani/Yr	0.58	-
Camel ¹	Carting	40	76	36	1.90

(Market prices fetched by the farmers for calculating the gross return is taken as Guar @ Rs. 2200/Q, Moth @ Rs. 2100/Q, Milk @ Rs.10/kg, and Wool @ Rs. 85/kg).

CONCLUSION

In view of many natural impediments, mainly the climatic conditions and poor soil moisture regime, the Thar desert appears to be more suitable for livestock farming than crop farming. Therefore, to ensure a regular income and sufficient food for farmers and better living standards, it is necessary to go for some other alternate land use-based farming system or subsidiary enterprises, which will provide more income and employment to the farmers. Such enterprises include camel rearing/ carting or other species. It holds practical

values for cost effectiveness, sustainable environmentally friendly and socio culturally acceptable. The main advantage of this study is to create awareness among the otherwise ignorant farmers regarding the usefulness of camel carting. The idea of sustainability of agriculture and livestock production revolves around better utilisation of time, money, resource and family labours of the farmers. So there is sign of hope to explore the income through camel carting that exists for turning the farmer economy viable.

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